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Collective profile of questionable publishing¹

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Introduction

Questionable publishing has been accused of its profit-oriented business model. Researchers, indexing services, and government attempt to distinguish questionable journals and publishers from others, and so-called black lists have been proposed (Beall, 2016; Anderson, 2017). Indexing services have its own criteria, e.g., self-citations, to discontinue suspicious journals. Yet a concrete and quantitative standard is still being constructed. Nevertheless of these efforts, questionable journals' market size is increasing. Many questionable journals are still indexed and justify their legitimacy by the authority. Also, some of questionable journals have high metric score. Along with the fast and easy peer review, they attract authors who need an academic output.

On the one hand, questionable journals increases their journal impact even though they are rarely cited (Kulczycki *et al.*, 2021; Moussa, 2021) and their publication distribution is skewed (Frandsen, 2017). One study found that their citations come from other indexed journals (Kulczycki *et al.*, 2021). The controversy on the increasing citations with their risk of publication system provides a question about how and who do they accumulate citations. On the other hand, questionable publishing has been understood as the problem of academic periphery. Early-stage authors and less-developed countries have been publishing in questionable journals (Sterligov & Savina, 2016; Macháček, Srholec & pro demokracii a ekonomickou analýzu (projekt), 2017). Studies provide quantitative profile of academic inequality: the academic system is stratified (Cole & Cole, 1974; Jones, Wuchty, & Uzzi, 2008)

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and bias on gender, race, and country (Huang *et al.*, 2020; Kozłowski *et al.*, 2022; Nielsen & Andersen, 2021; Sekara *et al.*, 2018). In this point of view, the controversy of predatory publishing of academic periphery countries is based on the disparity of academic inequality.

In this paper, we quantitatively gauge the collective characteristics of questionable publishing with massive publication data. We conduct a citation and country-wise publication analysis to gauge the current state of questionable journals. The academic state is critical to the analysis, since a result without considering the academic state leads to a biased conclusion (Macháček, V., & Srholec, M., 2021). We conduct a controlled experiment to minimize the bias. We used the bibliographic data of publications from the January 2019 dump of Scopus CUSTOM XML DATA. We matched 766 questionable journals in Beall's list with the Scopus dataset using ISSN (You *et al.*, 2021). We selected unquestioned journals for each questionable journal that are similarity-located in terms of the academic field, number of publications, and journal impact. The comparison with academically similarly-located journals highlights the malpractices of questionable journals in academia.

Results

The comparison of citation sources reveals that questionable journals exchange their citations to increase their citation impact, by avoiding self-citations. Self-citation rate of questionable journals is similar to unquestioned journals but shows a low self-reference rate (Figure 1A). We found that questionable journals exchange citations with other questionable journals, which is significantly higher than unquestioned journals (Figure 1B). We also found that about 90% of citations of these self-favorable citations arise within the same publisher. To quantitatively gauge the self-favorable citations within the publisher, we define a publication solidarity index (ψ) as follows:

$$\psi = \frac{1}{\sum_{j|j \in P_i} N_j} \cdot \frac{\sum_{j|j \in P_i} R_r(i;j) / Q_r}{\sum_{j|j \in P_i} R_c(i;j) / Q_c},$$

where R_r and R_c computes the rate of references and citations between the journal i and other journals in the publisher, Q_r and Q_c are the average reference and citation rate of the publisher, and N_j is the number of publications of the journal j . The reference and citations rate of a journal compute the self-favorable citations to the publisher. The average rate and the number of publications are designed to compensate for biases. Therefore, ψ computes the self-favorable citing behavior of a journal to the publisher with considering the academic landscape. The result exhibits that questionable journals produce more self-favorable citations than unquestioned journals (Figure 1C). The two exceptional journals are determined that are excluded from the list.

Figure 1. Citation profile of questionable (QJ) and unquestioned journals (UJ). (A) Journal self-citation, (B) citation exchange between QJs and UJs, and (C) publication solidarity index (ψ) of QJ compared with ψ of UJ.

Figure 2. Academic positions and impact of questionable (QJ) and unquestioned journals (UJ). (A) Centrality distribution of QJ, UJ, and all other Scopus journals and their differences. (B) Average disruptiveness score (Wu, Wang, & Evans, 2019) of questionable and unquestioned publications.

We found that questionable journals are located in the less important position of the academia, even though the questionable journals exchange citations to increase their impact. Centrality in the journal citation network shows that questionable journals have lower centrality scores than unquestioned journals, except for the PageRank centrality (Figure 2A). The high PageRank centralities of questionable journals imply that they exchange citations more than others. Moreover, a low average disruptiveness score (Wu, Wang, & Evans, 2019) shows that questionable journals publish more developmental research (Figure 2B).

The publication trajectory shows that authors in the major countries produce an increasing amount of publications in questionable journals. The number of publications in the top 5 high GDP countries is % of the total questionable publications. The questionable publication rate in these high GDP countries is not high, because the total number of publications in these countries is significantly high. Nevertheless, we found that the preference for questionable publications is increasing in high GDP countries. The authors in low GDP countries publish in questionable journals than unquestioned journals in 2010, but the rate decreased in 2018. The correlation with GDP was negative in 2010 but changed in 2018. We compute the normalized revealed comparative advantage (NRCA), which can capture the relative preference of questionable publishing relative to the number of publications in the country.

Figure 3. Country-wise trend of questionable publishing. (A) Number of questionable and unquestioned publications. (B) Rate difference between questionable and unquestioned publications. (C) Normalized Revealed Comparative Advantage (NRCA) difference between questionable and unquestioned publications in the country.

The NRCA of high GDP countries increases in 2018, meaning that authors in high GDP countries increase to publish more questionable publications, even though they produce lots of publications in academia.

The aforementioned trend in the number of publications may indicate that questionable publishing is not the problem of not only countries within academic boundaries but also countries in the academic center. However, the evidence that lots of questionable journals are located in low GDP countries left an unanswered question that who actually contributes to the growth of questionable journals. Although the authors in the academic center produce many publications, when the publications are concentrated in a small number of journals and other questionable journals are dominated by authors in the academic periphery, we may conclude that questionable publishing is dominated by authors in the academic periphery. To better understand the publishing trend, we analyze the proportion of dominant country in a journal. The distribution shows that dominant country in questionable journals produces less publications (Figure 4A). The dominant country produces more than 60% of publications in 15% of questionable journals, while more than 60% of publications in 34% of non-questionable journals. In other words, one single country produces significant amount of publications in only 15% of questionable journals, which means a regional feature. In 85% of questionable journals many countries produce large amount of publications.

We cannot directly match the regionality from the dominance of the country in the journal. We found that 77.7% of questionable journals are located in the dominant country, which implies that only a small portion of questionable journals are regional. We found, however, that some journals are located in the neighbor country but with unrevealed reasons. We expand the concept of neighbor with geographical distance and number of co-works to gauge the regionality of journals. We chose 5 topologically closed countries in geographical and co-work network as neighbor country. The result reveals an existence of regional journals in non-questionable journals, but questionable journals have less relations on geographical distance and co-work (Figure 4B and C). Neighbor countries of the journal's country produce most of publications in the non-questionable journals, in both geographical and co-work neighbors. Questionable journals, however, rarely show a neighbor's proportions. The result clearly depicts that most of questionable journals shows non-regional characteristics.

Figure 4. KDE plot of country's proportions in a journal: (A) dominant country, (B) geographical neighbors, and (C) co-work neighbors.

Discussion

In this paper, we quantitatively gauge the collective profile of questionable publishing with massive citation and publication data. The citation source reveals the self-favorable citation

within the publisher that increase its academic impact. The country of questionable publications shows that large amount of questionable publications are produced by authors in academic center. Moreover, the distribution of country's publications in the journal reveal that only a small amount of questionable journals are dominated by a single country, and authors in diverse countries publish in large amount of questionable journals.

This study of massive trend provides the warning of questionable journals that a small case study may omit. The results show the overall trend of questionable publishing, but not highlight the individual behavior of predatory journals. For instance, our study reveal that the dominance of one country arose in a small number of journals (Zhang *et al.*, 2022) but these questionable behavior should not be omitted. Constructing the comparative journals will provide a sophisticated comparison but may contains potentially questionable journals. Also, additional analysis with other massive dataset and lists will provide a more information on dynamics of questionable publishing.

Questionable publishing has become an increasing problem in academia. The publication trajectory clearly reveal that more and more publications are produced by questionable publishing system, not only for the authors in low GDP countries, but also for authors in high GDP countries. Under the suspicion of unqualified publications from their poor peer review, the incremental of questionable publishing should be aware. Moreover, the high citation exchange in questionable journals makes the journals seem legitimate comprised with the authority. More sophisticated study to reveal their mechanism on how they survive from indexing services is left for a further study.

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